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Research Article

**COMBINATION OF ABELMOSCHUS ESCULENTUS LINN &
BALANITES ROXBURGHII FOR ANALGESIC ACTIVITY****Swati Karande,* Shirish Patil, Tabbusam Shikalgar, Dr Nilofer Naikwade, Dr Padma Ladda, Sudhir Patil.**

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Abstract:

To evaluate the analgesic activity of fractions & residue of methanolic extract of Abelmoschus esculentus seeds & pericarpium of Balanites roxburghi. In Ayurvedic, the fruit of the allied species Balanites aegyptiaca is being used as analgesic. The tribal people are using the aqueous juice of Abelmoschus esculentus seeds & pericarpium of B. roxburghii for relieving the pain & inflammation. Mice were used as experimental animals and administered test drugs orally. Finally, screening of analgesic of crude extracts of A. esculentus & B. roxburghii, at the doses of 50 and 100 mg/kg on mice. Evaluation by hot plate method and acetic acid induced method was carried successfully. The present study conclude that combination dose gives significant results than alone group.

Keywords: analgesic activity, A. esculentus, B. roxburghii, mice.**Corresponding author:****Swati Karande,**Shri Appasaheb Birnale College of Pharmacy,
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INTRODUCTION:

Among the total prescription, analgesic and anti-inflammatory drug are the foremost medication in terms of frequency of use. Every day they are taken by more than 30 million people worldwide; of these, 40% of consumers are older than 60. Only 4.5% of the prescription are for so-called centrally acting analgesics, namely the opioids. Population studies have shown that 10-20% of all people who are 65 years older either are currently receiving or have recently received a prescription for nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs for arthritis. The very frequent use of NSAID's is based on the fact that these agents have many indications for which a large number of patients exist. These indications include chronic polyarthritis, psoriatic arthritis, osteoarthritis, gout, inflammatory soft tissue rheumatism, low back pain[1].

Analgesic drug relieves from mild to moderate pain, and reduces inflammation and fever. These agents are effective for somatic pain (e.g. musculoskeletal pain in joints, muscle and head ache). They are not effective in reducing discomfort from visceral organ (Heart, liver and lung). All these analgesic agents results into their therapeutic effects by inhibiting various prostaglandins substances involved in development of pain and inflammation and regulation of body temperature.

Pain is often associated with inflammation. Inflammation is normal response to any noxious stimulus that threatens the host and many vary from localized response to a generalized one. It is complex process involving release of chemicals from tissues and migrating cell and various mediators such as prostaglandins, leukotrienes and platelet activating factors. Tissue injury induces a series of reactions with release of pro inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL- β , IL-6, IL-8, followed by subsequent inflammatory reactions. In inflammatory disease like Rheumatoid arthritis, the inflamed tissue produces elevated levels of prostaglandin such as PGE1 and PGE2, increase local blood flow and potentiate the effect of mediators like bradykinin that cause increased vascular permeability [2].

The present available potent synthetic drugs having greater their side effect, toxicity and reappearance of symptoms. Hence it is essential to search for new anti-inflammatory agent that retain therapeutic efficacy and devoid of adverse effects are justified [3].

Medicinal herbs have been used as a form of therapy

for the relief of pain throughout history considering that the most important analgesic prototypes (e.g. salicylic acid and morphine) were originally derived from plant sources, the study of plant species traditionally used as pain killers should be seen as a fruitful research strategy in the search of new analgesic and anti-inflammatory drugs [4].

With the advancement of modern medicine, and the invention of newer and newer analgesics, nowadays it is also possible to relieve very severe pain, even cancer pain at its last stage. But the toxic and deleterious effects of most of the analgesics are often the limiting factors. Most of them create ulceration in the gastric mucosa as well as show nephrotoxic effect also. As a result, scientists and doctors are always in search of newer analgesics having less toxic effects. Often the herbal medicines show less toxicity than the synthetic products; as well as shows efficacy comparable to that of standard drug [5].

Abelmoschus esculentus Linn seed plays a significant role in the human diet due to presence of carbohydrate, minerals and vitamins[09]. Chemical constituent present in *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn they may be responsible for Analgesic activity- Ascorbic acid, Beta sitosterol, copper, Quercetin, Salicylates, Stigmastriol, Thiamin, Tryptophan, Zinc[10]. Further the Methanolic extract of *A. esculentus* Linn Fruits & seed was evaluated, for Analgesic activity & it exhibited potent Analgesic activity [6].

Balanites roxburghii is a medicinal herb and it's Preliminary phytochemical investigations have revealed the presence of saponin glycosides, flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, phenols from different parts of this plant. As the Fruit of this plant contain flavonoidal compound & several flavonoids isolated from medicinal plants have been reported to possess Analgesic activity, pericarpium of *B. roxburghii* showed analgesic activity, may be due to it's flavonoid compound. However it is observed that the pericarpium of *B. roxburghii* possesses analgesic activity but it is not show significant result. Hence present research work will analyse the possible potentiation of the analgesic effect of *B. roxburghii* & *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn[11].

2. NEED OF INVESTIGATION:

It is believed that some current analgesic drugs as opioids and Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) are not useful in all cases because of various side effects. Morphine causes acute morphine poisoning, hypotension, dependence etc, while the

NSAIDs causes gastric irritation, bleeding, ulcers and perforation. As a result searches for other alternatives are still essential [4].

NSAIDs Which are used as Analgesic they have their own side effects such as, nausea, vomiting, stomach pain and heartburn, stomach ulcers, headaches and dizziness, ringing of the ears, allergic reactions such as rashes, throat swelling, liver and kidney problems, high blood pressure, heart attack [7].

With the development of more and more synthetic drugs which have their unique adverse effects, it is imperative that we turn our attention to possible remedies that may be found among indigenous herbal plants.

Extracts from plants are used by the practitioners of traditional medicine for treatment of different diseases. Often, use of these plants is neglected by the practitioners of modern medicine. But many a times it has been found to act much better than the synthetic medicines [8].

However it is observed that the pericarpium of *B. roxburghii* possesses analgesic activity but it is not show significant result. Hence present research work will analyse the possible potentiation of the analgesic effect of *B. roxburghii* by *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn.

3. MATERIALS AND METHOD:

3.1 MATERIALS USED DURING EXPERIMENT-

3.1.1. Animals:-

Species- Swiss Albino Mice (male/female)

Body Weight- 18 – 25 gm, The experimental protocol [IAEC/ABCP/04/2017-2018] was approved by the IAEC.

3.2 Plant material processing:-

3.2.1. Collection and Authentication of Plant:-

1) The seeds of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn. Was collected from local region of Kole, Tal-Sangola, Dist-Solapur. Maharashtra.

2) The pericarp of *Balanites roxburghii* Was collected from local region of bhilawdi, Tal-Palus, Dist-Sangli.

Formula:-

$$\% \text{Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Test drug latency} - \text{Control Latency}}{\text{Cut off time} - \text{Control latency}} \times 100$$

The plants were authenticated by Mr.M.D.Wadmare, Asso.Prof. & Head, Department of botany at Smt. Kasturbai Walchand College, Sangli.

3.2.2. Drying:-

The seeds and pericarp of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn. and *Balanites roxburghii* respectively were separated from plants and shed dried under normal environmental conditions.

3.2.3. Extraction:-

The dried seeds of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn and pericarp of *Balanites roxburghii* were powdered coarsely using mixture grinder and passed through sieve no. 40. The powdered material were extracted by using soxhlet apparatus with 95% Methanol as a solvent for 48 hours at 640C. Extracts were cooled at room temperature & kept in desiccator to remove the moisture. Then the extract was dissolved in distilled water just before oral administration.

3.3. Toxicity study [6, 13]

In previous research work of K.Thirupathiet.al.indicated that 2000mg/kg dose of Methanolic Extract of pericarp of *Balanites roxburghii* was found to be safe. As well as according to ShabrinaJahanShammi et.al. 1000mg/kg dose of Methanolic extract of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn seeds was found to be safe. Hence in present research work we have selected 100mg/kg dose for both plants.

3.4. Experimental Procedure [12]

3.4.1. Analgesic activity:-

3.4.1.1. Hot plate method:-

Animals were divided into seven groups, each group containing six animals of either sex, with an initial weight 18 to 25g was used for each dose. The hot plate, which is commercially available, consists of an electrically heated surface. The temperature is controlled for 550 to 560C. This can be a copper plate or a heated glass surface. The animal was placed on the hot plate and the time until either paw licking or jumping occurs was recorded by a stopwatch. The latency was recorded before and after 15, 30, 60, 90, and 120 min of administration of the vehicle, standard or the test compound.

**Experimental design:
Hot plate method:-**

Sr. No.	Group	Dose	Treatment
1	Control	10ml/kg	D.W. given P.O. 60 min.prior to animal placed on hot plate
2	Standard (Pentazocine)	10ml/kg	STD. given I.P. 30 min. prior to animal placed on hot plate.
3	M.E seed of A.E	100mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min .prior to animal placed on hot plate.
4	M.E pericarp of B.R	100mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min .prior to animal placed on hot plate.
5	Combination of M.E of seeds of A.E. + M.E pericarp of B.R	100mg/kg + 50mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min .prior to animal placed on hot plate.
6	Combination of M.E of seeds of A.E. + M.E. pericarp of B.R	50mg/kg + 100mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min .prior to animal placed on hot plate.
7	Combination of M.E of seeds of A.E. + M.E. pericarp of B.R	50mg/kg + 50mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min .prior to animal placed on hot plate.

3.4.1.2 Acetic acid writhing method:-

Animals were divided in to seven groups, each group containing six animals of either sex. Mice in groups of six each was treated with vehicle, standard & test compounds. Analgesic activity of test drug was

Formula:-

assessed by counting the number of writhes induced by 1% acetic acid. Number of writhes per animal was counted for 10 min.

$$\% \text{Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Mean writhes of Control} - \text{Mean writhes of Test}}{\text{Mean writhes of Control}} \times 100$$

Acetic acid writhing method:-

Sr. No.	Group	Dose	Treatment
1	Control	10ml/kg	D.W. given P.O. 60 min.prior to I.P. injection of acetic acid.
2	Standard (Pentazocine)	10ml/kg	STD. given I.P. 30 min.prior to I.P. injection of acetic acid.
3	M.E seed of A.E	100mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min.prior to I.P. injection of acetic acid.
4	M.E pericarp of B.R	100mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min.prior to I.P. injection of acetic acid.
5	Combination of M.E of seeds of A.E. + M.E pericarp of B.R	100mg/kg +50mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min.prior to I.P. injection of acetic acid.
6	Combination of M.E of seeds of A.E. + M.E. pericarp of B.R	50mg/kg +100mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min.prior to I.P. injection of acetic acid.
7	Combination of M.E of seeds of A.E. + M.E. pericarp of B.R	50mg/kg +50mg/kg	Extract given P.O. 60 min.prior to I.P. injection of acetic acid.

3.3. Statistical analysis:-

Values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM for six rats in each group, statistical analysis was performed using one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's tests. (Graph Pad Instat 7.4.) $p < 0.05$ was taken as the criterion of statistical significance.

4. RESULT:**4.1. Analgesic activity:-**

4.1.1. Hot plate method:- Table no. 4.1.1. indicated that the group received MEBR+MEAE (100+50mg/kg) showed maximum increases in latency period at 60 min when compared with control group for Analgesic activity on Eddy's hot plate model.

Table no.4.1.1. Effect of Methanolic extracts of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn & *Balanites roxburghii* on Eddy's Hot plate method.

Sr.no	Treatment	Dose	Mean Latency period (sec)					
			0min	15min	30min	60min	90min	120min
1.	Control (D.W.)	10ml/kg	4.667 \pm 0. 1361	5.333 \pm 0. 1361	5.667 \pm 0.1721	5.833 \pm 0. 2871	6.00 \pm 0.2789	6.167 \pm 0.2453
2.	Pentazocine	10ml/kg	5.667 \pm .0860***	7.667 \pm .1361***	14.00 \pm .1053***	14.5 \pm .0912***	11.83 \pm .1 255***	10.33 \pm .0860***
3.	MEAE	100mg/kg	5.5 \pm .1748**	7.333 \pm .1721**	8.5 \pm .091**	10.67 \pm 0.136**	8.833 \pm 0. 068**	7.667 \pm 0.086**
4.	MEBR	100mg/kg	5.679 \pm .1721**	7.167 \pm .2453**	8.167 \pm 0.245**	11.33 \pm .2453**	8.833 \pm .1255**	7.833 \pm .1255**
5.	MEAE+ MEBR	100mg/kg + 50mg/kg	5.833 \pm .1949**	7.333 \pm .2018**	8.333 \pm .2277**	11.33 \pm .1748**	9.00 \pm .1491**	7.333 \pm .1361**
6.	MEBR+ MEAE	100mg/kg + 50mg/kg	5.607\pm .1721***	7.833\pm.1 639***	8.833\pm .1255***	11.67\pm .1361***	9.333\pm.1 361***	7.833\pm .1255***
7.	MEAE+ MEBR	50mg/kg + 50mg/kg	5.667 \pm .1721**	6.833 \pm .1639**	7.833 \pm .1639**	10.33 \pm 0. 086**	8.833 \pm .068**	7.333 \pm .1361**

All the values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM. The results were statically analysed by the one-way ANOVA followed by dunnett's test (n=6) , *** $p < 0.05$ as completed to control group.

Fig.no.4.1.1.Effect of Methanolic extracts of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn & *Balanites roxburghii* on Eddy's Hot plate method.at 0min, 15min,30 min,60 min,90 min 120 min respectively.

4.1.2.Acetic acid writhing method:- Table no 4.1.2Indicated that the group received MEBR+MEAE (100+50mg/kg) showed %

inhibition(59.45%) when compared with control group for analgesic activity on Acetic acid induced writhing model.

Table no.4.1.2.Effect of Methanolic extract of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn & *Balanites roxburghii* on Acetic acid writhing method.

Treatment	Number of writhing Mean \pm SEM	% inhibition
control (10ml/kg) (D.W.)	61.67 \pm 1.202	—
Pentazocine (10ml/kg)	0.6667 \pm 0.3333***	98.92
MEAE (100mg/kg)	35.67 \pm 1.647**	42.16
MEBR (100 mg/kg)	35.67 \pm 1.647**	51.08
MEAE+MEBR(100+50mg/kg)	28.67 \pm 0.9888**	53.05
MEBR+MEAE(100+50mg/kg)	25.67 \pm 1.687***	59.45
MEAE+MEBR(50+50mg/kg)	35.00 \pm 1.602**	43.23

All the values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM. The results were statically analysed by the one-way ANOVA followed by dunnett's test (n=6) , *** p <0.05 as completed to control group.

Fig.no.4.3.2.1. Effect of Methanolic extract of *Abelmoschus esculentus*Linn&*Balanites roxburghii* on Acetic acid writhing method.

5. DISCUSSION:

The toxic and deleterious effect of most of the analgesics are often the limiting factor. Most of them create ulceration in the gastric mucosa as well as show nephrotoxic effect also. As a result, scientists and doctors are always in search of newer analgesics having less toxic effects. Often given herbal medicines show less toxicity than the synthetic products; at times the herbal products show efficacy comparable to that of standard drug[5].

Hence for present research work we have selected following medicinal parts for screening of analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn seeds and *Balanites roxburghii* pericarp.

Chemical constituent present in seeds of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn are, Ascorbic acid, Beta sitosterol, copper, Quercetin, Salicylates, Stigmastinol, Thiamin, Tryptophan, Zink[10].

Chemical constituent present in pericarp of *Balanites roxburghii* are, saponin, glycosides, flavonoid, tannins, phenols[11].

This may provide some pharmacological rationale for the traditional use of this plants in pain& inflammation. Several flavonoids isolated from medicinal plant have been reported to possess analgesic activity. As both the plants contains flavonoidal compounds; the analgesic activity and anti-inflammatory activity may be due to them[13].

In **Eddy's hot plate test** MEAE,MEBR increased the latency time in mice. This model is used to screen the central analgesic effect in animal models.

Acetic acid induced writhing response is a sensitive procedure to evaluate peripherally acting analgesic and represents pain sensation by triggering localized inflammatory response, leads to the release of free arachidonic acid from tissue phospholipid mediated by peritoneal mast cells, acid sensing ion channels and the prostaglandin pathway.

Our results reveals that the combination of Methanolic extract of Pericarp of *Balanites roxburghii*& Methanolic extract of seeds of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn at dose **100mg/kg+50mg/kg** respectively shows

significant analgesic activity in eddy's hot plate models and Acetic acid induced writhing test when compared to control group. Further present results indicate that there is a gradual increase in latency period and maximum effect obtained at 60 min in hot plate model. & maximum percentage inhibition (59.45%) in acetic acid induced writhing method in combination of Methanolic extract of Pericarp of *Balanites roxburghii* and Methanolic extract of seeds of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn. at dose 100mg/kg+50mg/kg respectively.

Thus present studies provide a scientific data for the medicinal use of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn and *Balanites roxburghii* there by justifying its use in the Indian traditional system of medicine

6. CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that-

- Combination of Methanolic extract of seeds of *Abelmoschus esculentus* Linn & pericarp of *Balanites roxburghii* showed significant improved Analgesic activity than alone.
- Further studies are required to pinpoint active constituent responsible for the above actions, hence there is need to investigate various phytochemical constituent, so as a potent remedy will be available to treat the discomfort due to pain.
- Hence identification of active Phytoconstituent present in the seeds & pericarp by using modern analytical techniques will be the future scope of this study.

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